

The Effects of Wealth on Eco-centric and Anthropocentric Environmentalism: A Statistical Approach using the World Values Survey.

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ABSTRACT

Traditionally, eco-centric and anthropocentric forms of environmentalism have been described as mutually exclusive. Research suggests that different values predict each type of attitude, and those eco-centric attitudes, in particular, are strongly correlated with higher wealth. The objective of this paper is to characterize the relationship between eco-centric and anthropocentric attitudes across 43 countries. This study analysed secondary data from the 2005 World Values Survey, using a standard linear regression approach. It is shown that eco-centric and anthropocentric attitudes are not mutually exclusive, and that the predominance of one over the other is best predicted by a country's level of wealth.

Key words: Anthropocentric, eco-centric, pro-environmentalism, wealth. (Dunlap and Mertig, 1992) (Anon, 1992:P.2)

1. INTRODUCTION

In the 60s, increasingly number of social movements that advocated the protection of environmental resources took place. Part of the reason for these movements were the environmental damages left from the Second World War, concern for water and air pollution and their scarcity against the rapidly growing world population, as well as the use of nuclear power. Books such as *Silent Spring* (Carson, 1962) accentuated such concerns and presented environmental issues as “[a cause of] maladaptive human behaviour” (Milfont and Duckitt, 2004, p. 186). As concern for environmental issues proliferated, international and national actors across countries (e.g., Greenpeace, WWF, etc.) began to act in support of environmental protection. As a response to such public demands, and to redress the damaged caused, governments have implemented national regulations (e.g. driving restrictions to combat air pollution), systems and services (e.g. waste recycling, banning of dumping of toxic waste). Today, scientific evidence has shown that environmental issues, such as global warming or excessive plastic consumption, are attributed, largely, to human behaviour and lifestyle. Global warming, for example, has a series of repercussions on the environment, from severe drought to the increasing temperature in the oceans that causes coral bleaching; and these problems continue to worsen (Parry et al., 2004; Root et al., 2003). If large part of the environmental problems we face today are the result of our human behaviour, and the former continue to worsen, then this indicates that we have not modified significantly the ways we damage our environment for others that protect it. Thus, understanding what makes an individual adopt concern towards environmental issues, i.e. become pro-environmental, is essential for any initiative implemented to succeed, and the welfare of our planet.

In the following section, I present the theoretical arguments, found in the existing literature, that suggest the assumption of mutual exclusivity. Then, I describe the data and methods used in this study, followed by the results, and I conclude with the relevance of this study and potential future research.

2. Background: Pro-environmental Attitudes and Contextual Wealth

This study advances the account that it is more common for both types of attitude to overlap, but that the predominance of extreme-eco-centric or extreme-anthropocentric attitudes is a function of contextual wealth. Therefore, it focuses on aggregate-level data to allow for general comparisons. I argue that the predominance of extreme-eco-centric attitudes within a country increases as contextual wealth increases, while the predominance of extreme-anthropocentric attitudes decreases.

Attitudes are the evaluative dispositions or tendencies to make favourable or unfavourable statements or judgements” (Eagly and Himmelfarb, 1978, p. 528). Pro-environmental attitudes, then, refer to the concern to redress environmental problems and mitigate further environmental degradation because nature has value. Attitudes are shown to be the foundation for behaviours (Grob, 1995), the former are often the focus in the field of environmentalism, as does this work.

The conventional theory for pro-environmental attitude is post-materialism, coined by Inglehart (198). Post-material values are based on abstract goals, not material needs, such a freedom, welfare, belonging, including pro-environmental concern (addressed here as ‘attitudes’) (Blake, 2001; Inglehart, 1995, 1990). More specifically, the core argument is that as contextual wealth increases, so do post-material values—i.e. pro-environmental attitudes, in this case (Oreg and Katz-Gerro, 2006) because individuals in those contexts enjoy a stable material freedom that allows them to pursue more abstract goals (Inglehart, 1997, 1971).

There are two key drawbacks to Inglehart’s theory. First, it implies that societies of poorer countries cannot not hold pro-environmental attitudes because they are too preoccupied securing their basic material needs and safety; such as food, shelter, physical health and income. Second, he defines pro-environmental attitudes according to the phenomenon observed in the wealthiest countries (the Western, industrialized ones), and within these countries predominates an underlying eco-centric concern for nature Dunlap and Mertig contested the first drawback, with their theory of globalization of environmental concern.

The globalization theory (Dunlap and Mertig, 1997, 1995) argues that pro-environmentalism is not specific to rich countries, but that they were widespread. Their studies provided solid evidence that

residents of developing countries, even with their material limitations, are pro-environmental and in some cases even more so than their rich-country counterparts. Since then, several studies have provided evidence supporting this theory. Today, it is convention to deem pro-environmentalism a global phenomenon (Dunlap & Mertig, 1995, 1997; Diekmann & Franzen, 1999; Franzen & Meyer, 2010).

Dunlap *et al.* (2000) did notice, however, that Western, industrialized nations held a new attitude of the relationship between human and the natural world. Gagnon, Thompson and Barton defined this new attitude (1994) as eco-centric, where nature has intrinsic value and should be protected for its own wellbeing. They contrasted this attitude to the traditional one, anthropocentric, where nature is only valuable for what and how much resources it can provide to human.

While the dyad of eco-centrism and anthropocentrism provided empirical support for the gap in the literature that post-materialism could not explain, initially; studies that assess pro-environmental attitudes in these two types measure them using separate sets of survey questions and create separate indexes for them, implying that they are mutually exclusive. This study shows that, on the contrary, it is more common for both types of attitude to overlap, but the predominance of extreme-eco-centric or extreme-anthropocentric attitudes is better predicted by contextual wealth. This predominance of “extreme” attitudes is the focus of this study.

2.2 Data and Methods

The data comes from the World Values Survey (WVS) 2005-2009 wave and the World Bank. From the WVS dataset. The final working dataset consisted of 43 countries 54152 respondents, with about 1200 responses per country. The independent variable of primary interest comes from the World Bank data bank for 2005-2009. The method of analysis is simple and multiple linear regression of aggregate-level (national) data. The main dependent variable is the difference between the average anthropocentric attitude subtracted from the average eco-centric attitude per country; where 0 to 1 indicate none to extreme eco-centric; and 0 to -1 indicates non to extreme anthropocentric. Differences that fall between -0.1 and 0.1 represent eco-centric and anthropocentric attitudes that are equally strong, on average, in the corresponding country.

2.3 Results

The results show that the average eco-centric and anthropocentric attitude for countries tend to be similar, see Figure 2.1. However, the predominance of extreme attitudes does vary according contextual wealth, as theoretically predicted, Table 2.1. As, contextual wealth increases, so do extreme-eco-centric attitudes, while extreme-anthropocentric attitudes decrease. The main indicator of contextual wealth, GDP per capita, has the strongest effect across all models. Furthermore, when accounting for the overlap between attitudes the fit of the model is better, explaining 62 percent of the variance in the data.

2.4 Conclusion.

This study addressed the characterization of the relationship between eco-centric and anthropocentric attitudes across countries. Assessing the differences of means also addresses a common doubt that arises due to the intrinsic and abstract nature of attitudes, how does we know that we are measuring ‘truly’ eco-centric/anthropocentric? The answer is that we do not, and according to the findings in this study, we cannot assume that because they are often similar in strength. However, accounting for this overlap allows us to measure attitudes truer to their conceptual and operational definitions. This study also points to future cases of research, such as Switzerland or the United States, where although they have high national income (contextual wealth) their average eco-centric attitude is not the highest.

Figure 2. 1 Average strength of eco-centric and anthropocentric attitudes per country.

Table 2. 1 Linear regressions of average pro-environmental attitudes and extreme pro-environmental attitudes in 43 countries.

VARIABLES	(1) Country-average of eco-centric attitudes	(2) Country-average of anthropocentric attitudes	(3) Difference of country-averages
GDP per capita	0.0366 (0.0592)	-0.111 (0.0758)	0.148** (0.0599)
Political stability	0.0250 (0.0426)	-0.0739 (0.0547)	0.0989** (0.0431)
Country-average of household inc.	-0.0677** (0.0293)	-0.0628 (0.0375)	-0.00490 (0.0296)
Country-average of edu.	-0.0231 (0.0721)	-0.0463 (0.0924)	0.0231 (0.0729)
Constant	0.872*** (0.242)	1.299*** (0.310)	-0.427* (0.245)
Observations	43	43	43
R-squared	0.159	0.455	0.621

Standard errors in parentheses
 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

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